

RRI2SCALE – SES Questionnaire (M2.2)

Title: Regional multi-stakeholder dialogue (SES session) evaluation form

Description: The current questionnaire aims to measure the performance and impact of the RRI2SCALE regional multi-stakeholder dialogue (or the Scenario Exploration System - SES, as commonly called) that took place in each pilot region.

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

We are < Insert Regional Authority Name > and we are contacting you in the framework of RRI2SCALE, a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how we handle personal data is presented in the Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form.

Project: RRI2SCALE - Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy (GA Number 872526).

Partner: Organisation name: < Insert Regional Authority Name >

Address: < Insert Regional Authority Address >

Phone: < Insert Regional Authority Phone >

E-mail: < Insert Regional Authority Generic E-mail Address >

Responsible persons: 1. Project Manager: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

2. Data Protection Officer: < Insert Name > (< Insert email >)

What do we need from you?

We need you to participate in a short survey. It won't take you more than 7 minutes. Your replies will help us to evaluate the performance and impact of the key project activities. In this context, we need to process some of your personal data:

- Some basic demographics (gender, stakeholder group);

What will we do with your data?

The project's deliverables that the survey will derive will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. However, we are obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to the project's evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project auditing purposes.

How can you withdraw your consent?

You can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating by email or on the phone with the responsible persons listed above.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
1	My participation in a survey that will be carried out by RRI2SCALE to evaluate the performance and impact of key project activities, such as workshops and other materials.	

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Unde cided
1	PE.PR.4	Do you believe that the group of people who participated in the SES session was sufficiently large to allow a meaningful conversation?						
2	PE.PR.5	Do you believe that the group of people who participated in the SES session was adequately diverse to allow various opinions to be expressed?						
3	PE.PR.8	Do you believe that the SES session's facilitation (i.e., moderator, boards, and supportive material) allowed a meaningful conversation?						
4	SE.PR.1 , SP.DS.5	Did your participation in the SES session improve your understanding of potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect your region by 2022 and beyond?						
5	SE.PE.2	In the future, will you more actively search for information about controversial technologies (such as self-driving cars) because you participated in the RRI2SCALE SES session?						
6	PE.O.4, SP.EP.7	Did your participation in the SES session improve your understanding of any current dilemmas in your region (e.g., the dilemma of boosting innovation and economic growth at the expense of other social and environmental objectives)?						
7	PE.PE.2	Did your participation in the SES session increase your trust in the regional authorities?						
8	E.PE.1	Do you believe that analysing potential ethical issues must be an integral part of the strategic planning of the regional authority?						
9	E.PE.2	In the future, will you search more actively information about ethically controversial research-endeavours (such as mouse experiments) because you participated in the RRI2SCALE SES session?						
10	PE.O.5	Did meeting new people in the SES session lead (or may lead in the future) to new partnerships, networks, or network coalitions?						

11	SE.PR.2	Would you describe the SES session as a good opportunity for your region to advance towards awareness of the impact of science and technology on society?						
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Which is your region of residence?

- Vestland (Norway)
- Overijssel (the Netherlands)
- Kriti (Greece)
- Galicia (Spain)

You participated in this survey as a member of: (PE.PR.6)

- academia or research/ education
- governmental body / regional authority
- business
- civil society organisation
- local community
- other (please specify)

Gender: How do you identify? (GE.PR.1)

- Man
- Non-binary
- Woman
- I prefer to self describe, below:

#	Identifier	Question	Very much	Some what	Neutr al	Not really	Not at all	Undec ided
1	GE.PR.2	Do you believe that the SES session took place in a gender-equal environment?						
2	GE.PR.3	Did you observe any sexist language in the communication on the RRI2SCALE project?						
3	E.PR.1	Do you believe that the SES session complied with research integrity standards (e.g., clarity in the research goals, respect for all participants and transparency in data collection methods)?						
4	PE.PR.7	Do you believe that you had or were provided with sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to actively participate in the SES session?						

Q.1.1: What did you like the most about the SES session, or which aspect did you consider a weak part?